

Original Research

The Impact of Organizational Culture on the Accounting Information System and Operational Performance of a Municipality

Yassaman Khalili¹

Department of Accounting, Payame Noor University, Tehran, Iran

Mahdis Nikzad Ghadikolaei

Department of Accounting, University of Mazandaran, Babolsar, Iran

Mitra Rahi

Department of Accounting, Parsa Institute of Higher Education, Babolsar, Iran

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Abstract

One of the approaches to evaluating organizational culture is to understand its impact on the performance of an organization and also on accounting information systems. Since municipalities have moved towards a full accrual basis of accounting in recent years, the accounting information system has become more important to them than ever before, so the purpose of this research is to investigate the impact of organizational culture on the accounting information system and operational performance in municipalities in Mazandaran province. This research is applied in terms of purpose and descriptive-survey method. The statistical population of the research is all employees of municipalities in Mazandaran province and the sample size is 306 people, which was selected by random sampling. In the present study, the field method was used to collect primary data, and the primary data collection tool was a five-choice Likert questionnaire, and the library method was used to collect secondary data. The validity of the questionnaire was assessed using content validity and face validity, and its reliability was calculated using Cronbach's alpha, with a total reliability of 0.90. Structural equation modeling and Smart PLS software were used to test the research hypotheses. The results of the study showed that mission, participation, and stability have an effect on the accounting information system, and mission, participation, and adaptability have an effect on operational performance, and the accounting information system also has an effect on operational performance.

Keywords: Accounting information system, municipality, operational performance, organizational culture.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: y_khalili@pnu.ac.ir

Introduction

The important role of using the concepts and methods of accounting information systems in various organizations and companies to achieve organizational goals, continuous improvement of operations, and efficiency of decisions is obvious to everyone. The traditional accounting system cannot directly or indirectly establish a connection between the consumption of resources and the results obtained, and only collects costs. Most managers also pay attention to the same point of view and only care about the total costs of the organization in each of the cost categories, and the accounting system, which has been formed in this direction, strengthens the view of such managers. Managers use various tools and techniques for their decision-making in order to better manage organizations (Nakhaei, 2020). One of these tools is the accounting information system, which helps managers in decision-making in various ways. Today, for the sustainability of organizations and their long-term adaptation to their environment, they need to create and develop the necessary capabilities for survival and they need to have organizational health. Unlike financial accounting, which focuses primarily on past information, the accounting information system mainly provides information of a routine and current nature. Therefore, the main essence of the accounting information system is decision-making, and decision-making inherently deals with current and future events (Napitupulu, 2018). In order to be able to assist managers at different levels of the organization in decision-making and evaluation, the accounting information system must make the required information available in a detailed manner and as soon as possible. Therefore, the information of the accounting information system is useful when it is relevant, correct, reliable, and if estimated, is based on correct estimation procedures. The importance of this issue can be seen in the latest report of the World Economic Forum on Information Technology in Countries, which emphasizes the pivotal role of information and communication technology in development. This important issue has also been present in reports of international and national organizations (Ha, 2020). In addition to the accounting information system, an organization also needs an organizational culture.

Municipalities are considered the most important pillar of urban management. The life, survival and management of each city are based on the income of municipalities (Bayat & Asemannasab, 2021). Municipalities are in fact the highest level of urban planning and management in cities and, as an important institution, are responsible for providing services to citizens. They also require expenses to implement programs and provide services to citizens (Najafi et al., 2022). Since in today's turbulent world, all organizations inevitably face the phenomenon of change and the speed of these changes is increasing every day (Malek Hosseini et al., 2021), therefore, the municipal organization is no exception to this. Therefore, municipalities must create the necessary preparations and arrangements to face rapid changes and be able to increase their and their people's capabilities and capabilities in proportion to the changes in order to cope with them. Otherwise, the existing changes and turbulences will gradually drown them in death. Therefore, if municipalities want to survive and grow, they must make conscious changes in themselves, and managers must be able to provide rapid learning and reaction by using various mechanisms of the organization's culture for innovation and creativity, in order to meet the demands of the evolving society and increase their ability to control their destiny. Thus, it is better for municipalities to consciously change, innovate, and improve their organizational situation, especially in the area of accounting information system and

operational performance, otherwise changes will be imposed on them by the environment and if they are not prepared, they will inevitably face many problems. Considering the studies conducted, it was felt that there was no research on the effect of organizational culture on the accounting information system and considering operational performance from the perspective of municipal employees in Mazandaran province; therefore, it was decided to conduct a study in this field. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to identify and measure the effect of organizational culture on the accounting information system and operational performance of municipalities in Mazandaran province and to find an answer to the question of whether organizational culture has a significant effect on the accounting information system and operational performance of the municipality? Accordingly, this study provides implementation concepts for improving the accounting information system and operational performance in the municipality.

Theoretical Foundations

Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is one of the newest terms in management literature that has received much attention from management thinkers and experts in recent years (Hadid & Al-Sayed, 2021). According to Schein (2010), organizational culture is the most fundamental strength of any organization and business that leads to the sustainability of the organization and is an important factor for the long-term success of an organization. A strong organizational culture is cited as a factor in organizational success, while a weak organizational culture can create problems for the organization (Susilawati & Thiodora, 2023). Organizational culture is one of the most critical factors that control the ability, efficiency, endurance, and success of the organization, and management plays an important role in maintaining and maintaining organizational culture. Organizational culture is based on mutual trust, deep communication, and information technology support provided by one group or individual to another (Attar, 2020). Organizational culture is a major driver of innovation, productivity, and financial performance of companies (Binh, et al. 2022). Organizational culture guides the behavior of new members in organizations to solve problems (Schein, 2010). Some researchers (Deshpande & Webster, 1989) classify organizational culture as a culture that aims to help individuals understand how the organization functions. Several classifications have been proposed for organizational culture, for example, Quinn & Spreitzer (1991) divided organizational culture into four groups: developmental culture, group culture, rational culture, and hierarchical culture. Based on the four cultural characteristics of an effective organization, organizational culture is classified into four types: mission, adaptation, adaptability, and participation (Kwarteng & Aveh, 2018). Among other classifications, researchers (Chang & Lin, 2007) divided organizational culture into four types: stability, innovation, cooperation, and effectiveness (Binh, et al. 2022).

Accounting Information System

Due to the advancement of technology and the emergence of various and complex business models, the use of accounting information systems is essential for the daily operations of organizations (Mishra et al., 2023). Research on accounting information systems has always been an important topic among many researchers. An accounting

information system includes a set of related activities, documents and technological issues that are designed to collect, process and report information for the decision-making purposes of users of accounting information systems (Hurt, 2013) that uses financial and other resources to transform economic data into accounting information in order to meet the information needs of various users (Tilahun, 2019). Dameri et al. (2013) believe that the accounting information system is an integrated unit of information based on collected and related data. The accounting information system is a subsystem of organizational management information systems that aims to measure the financial performance of an organization and perform organizational accounting tasks. The data of this system is used by shareholders to evaluate the financial performance of the company, management to monitor the activities of the company and the government to ensure the effective use of the country's resources. Therefore, it plays a significant role in all economic and social dimensions (Ahmad et al. 2016). Other benefits of an accounting information system include increased performance, accuracy, faster processing, and better reporting (Zhu, et al. 2023).

Implementing an accounting information system involves the following steps:

A: Data Entry: In an accounting system, events are recorded based on primary documents as data into the system, including purchase invoices, sales invoices, receipts, and cash payments, etc. (Ha, 2020).

B: Data Processing: After data (primary documents) are entered into the accounting system, they are processed in the following order: Primary documents, after analyzing their impact on the assets, liabilities, expenses, revenues, and equity of the institution, are recorded as debits and credits in the accounting document sheet, as appropriate, and then transferred to the general journal. Entries made in the general and special journals are transferred to the relevant accounts in the general ledger. When the volume of financial events related to one or more general ledger accounts is large, specific ledgers or cards are used to have detailed information about each of these general ledger accounts (Kuchta & Sukpen, 2011).

C: Outputs: The result of data processing in an accounting system is the financial information provided, financial report statements, and the output of that system must be reliable, timely, accurate, concise, and useful, and relevant to the type of decision-making of decision-makers.

D: Feedback: The accuracy of recording financial events in the journal and transferring them to the general ledger at the end of each month is confirmed by preparing a trial balance. The trial balance is used as an output of the accounting system and a basis for controlling information processing as feedback, and based on it, some extracted information is re-entered into the accounting system as new data after changes to modify the accounting system (Nakhaei, 2020).

Operational Performance

The operational performance of an organization is widely studied in management and accounting studies. There are different perspectives on the definition of operational

performance of an organization. According to the study of Richard & Devinney (2009), the operational performance of an organization includes three main issues related to the operational performance of the organization:

- (1) Financial performance (profit, ROA or ROE).
- (2) Product performance in the market (sales or market share).
- (3) Shareholder return (shareholder dividend or economic value added) (Ha, 2020).

Felicio et al. (2014) have determined the operational performance of the organization in terms of increasing profits, reducing investment risks and acceptable competitiveness compared to competitors.

Theoretical Framework of Research Hypotheses

Organizational culture is an important category that can affect operational performance. Organizational culture is defined as a set of shared beliefs and values that influence the behavior and thinking of organization members and is considered a starting point for movement and dynamism or an obstacle to progress. Also, many experts consider organizational culture to be the most fundamental basis for fundamental change and transformation in the organization, in order to implement new programs. New programs and innovation are of great importance in organizations; because innovation is an important and vital factor for organizations to create sustainable value and competitive advantage in today's complex and changing environment. Organizations will be successful with greater innovation in responding to changing environments and creating and developing new capabilities that allow them to achieve better performance (Meng & Berger, 2019).

Denison (2000) believes that organizational culture is the main basis for creating values and beliefs from employees as well as managers, customers, shareholders, suppliers and others. Also, according to the results of Denison's (2000) research, organizational culture consists of four factors: mission, involvement in work, adaptability and stability. Accordingly, mission (responsibility) is considered as a key direction for the development of all organizations, so when organizations have a clear mission, they can perform well and achieve better results because they have a clear motivation and direction for the growth of their business (Kwarteng & Aveh, 2018). Organizational culture plays a vital role in realizing the mission and objectives of an enterprise, significantly influencing employees' attitudes toward the company (Yin & Lomonosov, 2019). Employees should understand the meaning of the mission (Dermol & Širca, 2018). An organization that integrates its mission into its culture fosters an environment where employees share values that embody the mission (Iltis, 2005).

Work involvement reflects the commitment of employees and a sense of ownership, participation in decision-making of all members of the company and the direction of the work of employees in that organization. Organizations that give their employees more autonomy by using team spirit and continuously seek to develop employee skills to motivate employees to participate in the work process in the organization achieve higher operational performance (Ha, 2020). Employee participation is an important aspect of

organizational culture that can enhance organizational identification (Kpakol et al, 2016). A culture of employee participation can improve organizational commitment (Ogu, 2024). Inclusive and participative environments, such as clan and adhocracy cultures, neither nurture nor inhibit authenticity (Reis et al, 2016). Additionally, a strong organizational culture, characterized by information disclosure and the participation of all members, can be developed to achieve organizational goals (Putra & Dewi, 2019).

Adaptability is the ability of the organization to make internal changes in the presence of external changes. If companies are internally focused, they face difficulties in fulfilling the external needs of the market, so ensuring the ability to make changes and understand customers is of great importance (Hadid & Al-Sayed, 2021). Organizational culture allows organizations to adapt effectively to change (Al-Azkiya et al, 2024). Adaptability is a key dimension of organizational culture, as highlighted by the Denison model (EL-Makarem, 2023). The importance of adaptability and continuous improvement is recognized in dynamic business environments (Ramsés et al, 2024).

Stability means the existence of a common set of rules for the organization's operation that has the effect of promoting working relationships between employees in a real and effective way at work. Organizations achieve better operational performance when these organizations are sustainable and their implementation is desirable. Companies should have a combination of participation and stability in their work processes to promote work processes more effectively (Denison, 2000). For example, ethical behavior shapes trust, compliance, and stability within sports management relationships (Kim, 2025). Organizational culture is also a factor of stability in the banking system. Stability in organizational culture is associated with control and order (Lund, 2003). Employee retention enhances the stability and continuous progress of employees, improves employee morale, and increases job satisfaction (Darko, et al. 2024).

The relationship between organizational culture and accounting information system has been investigated in various studies. The results of studies have shown that organizational culture significantly affects the quality and implementation of accounting information systems (AIS) (Yanti & Pratiwi, 2022; Jameel et al.2024, Susilawati & Thiodora, 2023; Nurliyani et al, 2020). A strong organizational culture is often associated with the success of an organization, while a weak culture can cause problems (Susilawati & Thiodora, 2023). Studies show that organizational culture affects both the quality of accounting information systems and the quality of accounting information itself (Pasaribu & Astuty, 2021; Yanti & Pratiwi, 2022). For example, Jameel et al. (2024) examined the mediating role of accounting information systems between organizational culture and organizational performance in small and medium-sized companies and showed a significant impact of organizational culture on AIS. Pasaribu & Astuty (2021) found that organizational culture affects the use of management accounting information systems as well as the quality of management accounting information.

On the other hand, other research examined the impact of accounting information systems on organizational performance. AIS plays a crucial role in shaping the financial performance of companies, particularly for Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs). Studies show a significant impact of timely, transparent, and accurate AIS on SMEs' financial performance, which highlights the importance of optimizing accounting

systems to boost competitiveness and sustainability (Lin et al. 2024). For instance, a study of industrial companies in Jordan indicated that effective AIS implementation enhances the relevance of information related to operational processes. Similarly, in Indonesia, research has demonstrated that energy efficiency and AIS efficiency positively and significantly impact both operational and environmental performance (Lutfi, et al. 2022). Accounting information systems (AIS) significantly impact a company's operational performance by streamlining processes, improving decision-making, and increasing overall efficiency. Effective implementation of AIS can lead to increased revenue growth, profitability, and better resource allocation, enabling businesses to respond quickly to market changes and identify growth opportunities. Furthermore, the integration of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence into AIS can increase the speed and accuracy of accounting processes, thereby improving decision-making, operational efficiency, and the quality of financial reporting (Lin et al. 2024; Siqani & Vokshi, 2023).

Based on the above analyses, this study has put forward the following hypotheses:

1. An organization's mission has a positive impact on the organization's operational performance.
2. An organization's participation has a positive impact on the organization's operational performance.
3. An organization's adaptability has a positive impact on the organization's operational performance.
4. An organization's stability has a positive impact on the organization's operational performance.

Companies are increasingly using information systems to sustain their performance (Kirchner-Krath et al, 2024). According to Marshall & Steinbart's (2017) research, there are three factors that affect the accounting information system: business strategy, information technology development, and organizational culture. Organizational culture has a positive relationship with the accounting information system. In order to provide and implement an accounting information system, it is of great importance to identify and understand the concept, standards, and strengths of an organization. The organizational culture factor is considered as the basis for the best accounting information system, and culture plays an important role in building a standard accounting information system. Therefore, in a company's financial statements, culture affects the accounting information system and executive approaches are influenced by its culture (Shao, 2019). Based on this analysis, other hypotheses of this study can be put forward:

5. Organizational culture (mission, participation, adaptability and stability) have a positive effect on the accounting information system.

Performance evaluation is essential to measure the efficiency of agents who manage resources on behalf of the employer. One of the issues raised in this context is the accounting information system, which can help managers achieve the best evaluations of the company's performance by measuring performance and providing useful internal information. The accounting information system is evaluated as an optimal tool to

improve the operational performance of an organization. In the case of an organization with a suitable accounting information system, all its activities are effective (Alagic, 2017). Kwarteng & Aveh (2018) have also stated that the accounting information system and operational performance have a positive relationship with each other, so that when the organization has a suitable accounting information system, the operational performance of the organization increases. Based on the above analysis, the last hypothesis of the study can be put forward:

6. The accounting information system has a positive effect on the operational performance of the organization.

Research Background

Foreign Background

Kotiloglu et al. (2024) analyzed the role of national culture as a proxy for collective interpretive processes that influence organizational decision-making in response to performance feedback. Their study showed that the influence of four dimensions of national culture including uncertainty avoidance, performance orientation, future orientation, and institutional collectivism is an important concept for the development of organizational performance. Susilawati & Thiodora (2023) concluded in a study that organizational culture affects the quality of accounting information systems, which in turn affects the quality of information. Mishra et al. (2023) presented a study that developed a post-adoption model of information systems that broadly reflects the reasons for user satisfaction and the goals of information systems continuity. Zhu et al. (2023) presented a research model and showed challenges and barriers, technology stress, and coping responses as key mechanisms related to accounting information system characteristics and burnout. Binh et al. (2022) studied the impact of organizational culture on the quality of accounting information systems in Vietnam. Their research findings showed that organizational culture is a key factor in increasing the quality of accounting information systems of Vietnamese companies. Also, implementing an innovative corporate culture improves the system quality and information quality of accounting information systems, which helps accounting information for adequate decision-making. Hadid & Al-Sayed (2021) conducted a study titled Management Accountants and Strategic Management Accounting: The Role of Organizational Culture and Information Systems. The results showed that there is a positive relationship between management accountants' networking and the implementation of strategic management accounting approaches. Unlike the quality of information systems, the moderating effects of this relationship through results-oriented culture and innovation-oriented culture are not empirically supported. Instead, innovation-oriented culture has a significant positive and indirect effect on the implementation of strategic management accounting through management accountants' networking, but this effect is not direct. Ha (2020) conducted a study titled The Effect of Organizational Culture on Accounting Information System and Operational Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Ho Chi Minh City. The results showed that mission, participation, and instability in organizational culture have a positive effect on the accounting information system of small and medium enterprises in Vietnam. In addition, mission, participation, and adaptability in organizational culture have positive effects on the operational performance of the

company. Another finding is that accounting information system has a positive effect on the operational performance of small and medium-sized enterprises in Vietnam. In a study, Huynh (2021) examined the effect of organizational culture on accounting information quality: the mediating role of accounting information system in Vietnam. The findings of this study showed that the adoption of accounting information systems in an organization mediates part of the effect of organizational culture on accounting information quality. Attar (2020) in a study titled *Organizational Culture, Knowledge Sharing, and Intellectual Capital: Directions for Future Research*, showed that organizational culture is positively related to intellectual capital. Meng & Berger (2019) conducted a study titled *The Effect of Organizational Culture and Accounting Performance on Public Relations Professionals' Job Satisfaction: Examining the Mediating Effects of Partnership and Trust*. The results showed that the mediating effects of partnership and trust on professionals' job satisfaction were significant when a supportive organizational culture and excellent leader performance were achieved. Tenji & Foley (2019) conducted a study titled "Investigating the Readiness of Organizational Culture Characteristics for Implementing Accounting Total Quality Management." The results showed how a theoretical framework can be applied in the workplace to assess readiness for implementing accounting total quality management. This study contributes to the literature by using a new theoretical model in the field of assessing readiness for implementing accounting total quality management. Shao (2019) conducted a study titled "The Interaction of Strategic Leadership Behaviors and Organizational Culture on Strategic Coordination of Accounting and Business Information Systems and Organizational Systems Integration." The results show that the effects of idealistic behaviors and inspirational motivational behaviors of leadership are extraordinary drivers for strategic coordination of accounting and business information systems, which have the greatest positive impact on organizational systems integration. In addition, flexible culture positively moderates the relationship between strategic leadership behaviors and strategic coordination of accounting and business information systems, while control-oriented culture negatively moderates these relationships. Napitupulu (2018) conducted a study titled *Organizational Culture in Management Accounting Information System: A Study of Indonesian State-Owned Companies*. The results showed that organizational culture affects the quality of accounting information system. The results also showed that the dimensions and indicators used to build the study model showed high value, meaning that the dimensions and indicators reflect organizational culture and quality of accounting information system in state-owned companies in Indonesia. Gichaaga and Aduda (2018) conducted a study titled *The Impact of Management Accounting Behaviors on Financial Performance of Manufacturing Companies in Kenya in the 2006-2011 Financial Period* using a descriptive method. The results showed that information related to decision-making practices is the most common management accounting method among manufacturing companies in Kenya, followed by strategic analysis, budgeting, performance evaluation, cost, size, and financial leverage. Hogan & Coote (2014) conducted a study titled *The Relationship Between Organizational Culture, Innovation, and Performance by Testing the Schein Model and Structural Equation Modeling in Australia*. The results showed how layers of organizational culture, especially creative norms and behaviors, to some extent moderate the effect of innovative ideas that support the measurement of firm performance.

Domestic Background

Setoudeh (2021) conducted a study entitled Investigating the Moderating Role of Organizational Culture on the Relationship between Accounting Information System and Operational Performance of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (Case Study: Companies in the Special Zone of Assaluyeh). The results showed that organizational culture has a moderating role on the relationship between accounting information system and operational performance of small and medium-sized enterprises in the Special Zone of Assaluyeh; therefore, using organizational culture indicators such as participation, instability, mission, and adaptability can, in addition to affecting the relationship between accounting information system and operational performance of small and medium-sized enterprises, be useful in creating innovations, technologies, and emerging technologies and facilitating the recording of accounting information. Malek Hosseini et al. (2021) conducted the effect of organizational culture through modern management accounting techniques on financial performance in companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange. The results show that organizational culture has an impact on the financial performance of companies by considering modern management accounting techniques. This research provides useful information to shareholders to select board members who have a high organizational culture and who can improve the company's financial performance by applying modern management accounting techniques. Abdipour et al. (2020) conducted a study entitled The Effect of Organizational Culture on the Effectiveness of Management Performance Auditing using the Structural Equation Modeling Approach. The results showed that organizational culture has a significant effect on the effectiveness of performance auditing. The results also showed a significant effect of various characteristics of organizational culture such as commitment to participation, adaptability, adaptability, and mission on the effectiveness of management performance auditing. Azizi et al. (2020) conducted a study entitled Presenting a Model of the Effect of Accounting Information Systems Characteristics on System Performance Based on the Moderating Role of Job Uncertainty. The results showed that the characteristics of the accounting information system have an effect on system performance. Another result of this study was that job uncertainty moderates the effect of accounting information system characteristics on system performance. Nakhaei (2020) conducted a study entitled the impact of accounting information system innovations on organizational culture. The results showed that there is a direct and significant relationship between the use of activity-based costing and activity-based management innovations and organizational culture. This study also showed that the application of management accounting concepts and methods and its innovations in companies plays a significant role in achieving organizational goals, continuous improvement of operations, and the efficiency of management decisions. Since organizational culture is important for the accounting profession, the acceptance and application of management accounting innovations in companies is a function of organizational culture. Alizadeh Loshabi & Karimi (2016) conducted a study entitled the study of the relationship between organizational factors (organizational culture, organizational commitment, and organizational structure) on the quality of accounting information systems in medical centers in Mashhad. The results showed that organizational culture and organizational commitment have a positive and significant effect on the quality of accounting information systems in medical centers in Mashhad, but the effect of organizational structure on the quality of accounting information systems in medical centers in Mashhad has been rejected. Khodabakhshi

(2016) conducted a study entitled *The Relationship Between Management Information Systems and Organizational Performance and the Role of Organizational Culture in the Adoption of Information Systems in Organizations in Tehran*. The results showed that information systems play an important role in the performance of organizations. Namamian & Feizollahi (2015) conducted a study entitled *The Effect of Organizational Culture on Organizational Performance with the Mediating Role of Innovation in Ilam Industrial Park, Tehran*. The results showed that organizational cultures (group, logical, developmental, hierarchical) with the mediating role of innovation have positive and significant effects on organizational performance, and the degree of influence of group culture with the mediation of innovation on performance is stronger than other cultures. Hajiha & Soltani (2014) conducted a study entitled *An Attitude to the Cultural Dimensions of Accounting in Tehran*. The results showed that the development and evolution of accounting is affected by various environmental factors, one of the most important of which is culture. Hajiha & Kharatzade (2014) conducted a study entitled *The Relationship Between Organizational Culture and the Application of Management Accounting Innovations in Companies Listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange*. The results showed that there is a significant difference between the organizational culture of companies that have implemented management accounting innovations and those that have used these innovations less. Also, the dimensions of supportiveness and goal orientation of culture are higher in groups that implement management accounting innovations. Zahedi & Nikandish (2013) conducted a study entitled *The Relationship Between Organizational Culture and Financial Performance in Subsidiaries of the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology based on the Denison Model*. The results showed that there is a significant positive relationship between each of the cultural characteristics variables with three indicators of return on assets, return on equity and return on sales, and a significant negative relationship between each of them with the ratio of operating expenses to operating income. This finding refers to the concept of the existence of a relationship between organizational culture and financial performance.

Research Methodology

This research is applied in terms of purpose and descriptive-survey in terms of method. The statistical population of the research includes all municipal employees in Mazandaran province, which constitute 1500 people. The sample selection method in this study was random sampling using software. To determine the required sample size, the Cochran limited population sampling formula was used. Based on the Cochran limited formula with an error of 5 percent, the sample size was 306 people, which was selected by the available random method. In the present study, the field method was used to collect primary data, and the primary data collection tool was a five-choice Likert questionnaire, and the library method was used to collect secondary data. The validity of the questionnaire was verified by content validity and face validity, and its reliability was calculated using Cronbach's alpha, with a total reliability of 0.90. Structural equation modeling and Smart PLS software were used to test the research hypotheses. In this study, following Ha (2020) a questionnaire was used to measure organizational culture, accounting information system, and operational performance. The use of other performance measurement methods and financial reporting could be a new topic for future investigation.

Research findings

Results of descriptive demographic statistics

In descriptive analysis, researchers summarize and classify the demographic data of the study using descriptive statistical indicators. In this section, the frequency percentage of the target population is described using frequency tables. Most of the respondents are 240 (78%) men and 66 (22%) women. Most of the respondents are 220 (72%) married and 86 (28%) singles from the sample. Based on the age distribution of the respondents, it can be seen that the age group of 31 to 40 years has the highest frequency. As 56% of the respondents are in this age group. However, the lowest age frequency was related to the 25-30 age group. As 6% of the respondents are in this age group. The highest age frequency is for 11-15 years of work experience with 23% (70 people), followed by 6-10 years of work experience with 19% (60 people), and finally 1 year of work experience with 1% (2 people). The highest percentage is made up of employees with a bachelor's degree with 54% (165 people). This group is followed by employees with a master's degree or higher with 36% (110 people), and respondents with an associate's degree with 7% (21 people), and finally respondents with a diploma degree with the lowest frequency with 3% (10 people). The highest percentage is made up of those with an expert organizational category with 39% (120 people), and finally respondents with another organizational category with the lowest frequency with 15% (45 people).

Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test is used to show whether the data distribution is normal or not. In fact, this test is a goodness-of-fit test for comparing a theoretical distribution with an observed distribution. If the decision criterion is greater than 0.05, the data distribution is normal and first-generation methods (based on the maximum likelihood approach) can be used, otherwise second-generation methods (based on the partial least squares approach) are used.

H0: The data have a normal distribution.

H1: The data do not have a normal distribution.

Table 1. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results

Variable	The value of the K-S statistic	Significance level	Result (normal/abnormal)
Mission	0/47	0/032	Abnormal
Participation	0/35	0/029	Abnormal
Adaptability	0/42	0/021	Abnormal
Stability	0/56	0/430	Abnormal
Accounting Information System	0/64	0/025	Abnormal
Operational performance	0/34	0/028	Abnormal

The above table shows that since the significance level of all components is less than 0.05 (Sig >0.05), the hypothesis H0 is rejected and the hypothesis H1 is confirmed. This means that the data follow a non-normal distribution and PLS structural equations can be used for the study.

Model analysis and hypothesis testing

Fitting measurement models

1- Checking reliability in the measurement model

Three criteria are used to check reliability: factor loading coefficient, Cronbach's alpha, and composite reliability.

A) Factor loading coefficients

Factor loadings are calculated by calculating the correlation value of the indices of a construct with that construct, which if this value is equal to or greater than 0.4, indicates acceptable reliability of the measurement model. If the factor loadings between the construct and its indicators are less than 0.4, those indicators (questionnaire questions) should be modified or removed from the research model. The factor loading values of the research indicators are shown in Figure (1).

Figure 1. Factor loading coefficients of research measures

According to the table, factor loading coefficients for all questions are greater than 0.4, which indicates that the sample has appropriate reliability.

b) Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability

According to the data analysis algorithm in the PLS method, after measuring the factor loadings of the questions, it is time to calculate and report the Cronbach's alpha coefficient and composite reliability of the constructs. Cronbach's alpha is a classic measure for reliability analysis and a suitable measure for assessing internal consistency. The degree of correlation between a construct and its related indicators is shown by internal reliability. The appropriate value for Cronbach's alpha is greater than 0.7. In order to calculate reliability, there is another measure called composite reliability (CR). To better measure the reliability of both of these measures, a value above 0.7 has been calculated for composite reliability. The values obtained from these two criteria are shown in Table (2).

c) Convergent validity

The second criterion for examining the fit of measurement models is convergent validity, which examines the degree of correlation of each construct with its questions (indicators). The AVE criterion is used by Smart PLS software for this purpose. Convergent validity is established when the value of all standardized factor loadings related to each of the measurement variables and the AVE value related to each of the latent variables is greater than 0.5. These values are shown in Table (2).

Table 2. Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, convergent validity

Hidden variables	Title	Cronbach's alpha coefficient (Alpha \geq 0/7)	Composite reliability coefficient (CR \geq 0/7)	Mean extracted variance (AVE \geq 0/5)
Mission	MS	0/930	0/955	0/877
Participation	IN	0/907	0/941	0/842
Adaptability	AD	0/913	0/945	0/852
Stability	CO	0/901	0/938	0/834
Accounting Information System	AI	0/911	0/944	0/849
Operational performance	OP	0/904	0/940	0/840

Given that the appropriate value for Cronbach's alpha is 0.7, for composite reliability is 0.7, and for AVE is 0.5, the results in Table (2) show that all these criteria have adopted appropriate values for latent variables, and the suitability of the reliability and convergent validity can be confirmed.

D) Divergent validity

Divergent validity is another criterion for examining the fit of the measurement model, which is used to examine divergent validity by comparing the correlation of a construct with its indicators against the correlation of that construct with other constructs, which is used through the Fornell-Larcker criterion (Table 3).

Table 3. Correlations between latent variables and AVE values

	Adaptability	Stability	Accounting Information System	Operational performance	Mission	Participation
Adaptability	0/923					
Stability	0/836	0/913				
Accounting Information System	0/839	0/875	0/921			
Operational performance	0/709	0/807	0/903	0/916		
Mission	0/863	0/840	0/865	0/766	0/936	
Participation	0/862	0/818	0/834	0/748	0/886	0/918

Based on the results obtained from the correlations and the AVE root placed on the diagonal of Table (3), the divergent validity of the model at the construct level can be concluded in terms of the Fornell-Larcker criterion.

2- Structural model fit

In the structural equation modeling method, the structural model fit can be examined through the criteria of significance coefficients Z values, t-values), R2 criterion and Q2 criterion. First, the standard estimate of the research model is obtained, which is the standard estimate of the parameters in the model. Now, after the above results, the significance of all existing relationships between latent and manifest variables is examined below.

A) Significance coefficients (t-value)

The most basic criterion for measuring the relationship between constructs in the model (structural section) is the t-significance numbers. The relationship between constructs and hypotheses is confirmed if the significant numbers exceed 1.96. This confirmation is based on a 95 percent confidence level. By default, PLS software tests relationships at a 95% confidence level, and since the t-value of this confidence level is 1.96, any relationship for which the t-value is outside the range of -1.96 to +1.96 is statistically confirmed at a 95% confidence level.

Figure 2. Significance coefficients of the conceptual model

As shown in the model, the hypotheses of the model except for the third and eighth hypotheses are accepted and their t values are outside the specified range, which indicates the significance of all hypotheses and relationships between variables at the 95% confidence level.

b) Coefficient of Determination (R²)

According to the study of Chin (1998), for the coefficient of determination R², three values of 0.19, 0.33, 0.67 are considered as the criterion values for weak, medium and strong values, respectively. According to the R² results, all endogenous variables of the model are greater than 0.67, which indicates a strong fit of the structural model.

Table 4. Coefficient of Determination Values

	Accounting Information System	Operational performance
R ²	0/831	0/830

c) Predictive power coefficient (Q²)

This criterion determines the predictive power of the model, and if the Q² value for an endogenous construct reaches three values: 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35, it indicates weak, medium, and strong predictive power of the related exogenous construct, respectively.

Table 5. Prediction power coefficient values

	Accounting Information System	Operational performance
Q ²	0/689	0/473

According to the results obtained, the Q2 values of the constructs are greater than 0.35 and show a strong fit of the structural model.

Testing the research hypotheses

First research hypothesis: The mission has a significant effect on the accounting information system.

According to the first hypothesis, based on the impact of the mission on the accounting information system, since its t-value is equal to (2.389) and is outside the range (-1.96 and 1.96), the hypothesis H₀ is rejected at a 99% confidence level and the hypothesis H₁, which is the researcher's hypothesis, is accepted with a path coefficient of (0.619), meaning the mission has an effect on the accounting information system.

Second research hypothesis: Participation has a significant effect on the accounting information system.

According to the second hypothesis, based on the effect of participation on the accounting information system, because its t-value is equal to (6.263) and is outside the range (-1.96 and 1.96), the hypothesis H₀ is rejected at a 99% confidence level and the hypothesis H₁, which is the researcher's hypothesis, is accepted with a path coefficient of (0.868), meaning that participation has an effect on the accounting information system.

The third hypothesis of the study: Adaptability has a significant effect on the accounting information system.

According to the third hypothesis, based on the lack of effect of adaptability on the accounting information system, because its t-value is equal to (1.077) and is in the range (-1.96 and 1.96), the hypothesis H₀ is confirmed at a confidence level and the hypothesis H₁, which is the researcher's hypothesis, is not accepted with a path coefficient of (0.135), meaning that adaptability does not have an effect on the accounting information system.

The fourth hypothesis of the study: Stability has a significant effect on the accounting information system.

According to the fourth hypothesis, based on the effect of stability on the accounting information system, because its t-value is equal to (3.135) and is outside the range (-1.96 and 1.96), the hypothesis H₀ is rejected at a 99% confidence level and the hypothesis H₁, which is the researcher's hypothesis, is accepted with a path coefficient of (0.426), meaning that stability has an effect on the accounting information system.

Fifth research hypothesis: Mission has a significant effect on operational performance.

According to the fifth hypothesis, based on the effect of mission on operational performance, because its t-value is equal to (5.171) and is outside the range (-1.96 and 1.96), the hypothesis H₀ is rejected at a 99% confidence level and the hypothesis H₁, which is the researcher's hypothesis, is accepted with a path coefficient of (0.739), meaning that mission has an effect on operational performance.

Sixth research hypothesis: Participation has a significant effect on operational performance.

According to the sixth hypothesis, based on the effect of participation on operational performance, because its t-value is equal to (8.751) and is outside the range (-1.96 and 1.96), the hypothesis H₀ is rejected at a 99% confidence level and the hypothesis H₁, which is the researcher's hypothesis, is accepted with a path coefficient of (0.587), meaning that participation has an effect on operational performance.

Seventh research hypothesis: Adaptability has a significant effect on operational performance.

According to the seventh hypothesis, based on the effect of adaptability on operational performance, because its t-value is equal to (2.737) and is outside the range (-1.96 and 1.96), the hypothesis H₀ is rejected at a 99% confidence level and the hypothesis H₁, which is the researcher's hypothesis, is accepted with a path coefficient of (0.832), meaning that adaptability has an effect on operational performance.

Eighth research hypothesis: Stability has a significant effect on operational performance.

According to the eighth hypothesis, based on the lack of effect of stability on operational performance, because its t-value is equal to (1.595) and is in the range (-1.96 and 1.96), the hypothesis H₀ is confirmed and the hypothesis H₁, which is the same hypothesis of the researcher, is not accepted with the path coefficient (0.160), meaning that stability does not affect operational performance.

The ninth hypothesis of the research: The accounting information system has a significant effect on operational performance.

According to the ninth hypothesis, based on the effect of the accounting information system on operational performance, because its t-value is equal to (6.536) and is outside the range (-1.96 and 1.96), the hypothesis H₀ is rejected at the 99% confidence level and the hypothesis H₁, which is the same hypothesis of the researcher, is accepted with the path coefficient (0.928), meaning that the accounting information system has an effect on operational performance.

Conclusion and suggestion

In this study, the effect of organizational culture on the accounting information system and operational performance of municipalities in Mazandaran province was investigated. By reviewing the research conducted, we realize that the subject of this study is unique in that it is in the municipal organization and is innovative in this respect. The overall results of the study showed that mission, participation, stability have an effect on the accounting information system and mission, participation and adaptability have an effect on operational performance and also the accounting information system has an effect on operational performance. The overall results of this study are similar to the study of Lin et al. (2024); Susilawati & Thiodora (2023) and Kotiloglu, et al. (2024). The separate examination of each hypothesis with previous studies is as follows:

In examining the test of the first hypothesis of the study on the impact of the mission on the accounting information system, it was determined that the results of examining this hypothesis are consistent with the results of previous research by researchers such as Setoudeh (2021), Azizi et al. (2020) and Napitupulu (2018). Considering the field and library findings of this study regarding the interpretation and interpretation of this hypothesis, it should be stated that in order to minimize human error in the organization's information processing network, this important task can be accomplished in an organization by using organizational culture, which leads to an increase in the acceleration of service provision to customers and, most importantly, to the improvement of organizational performance. Also, the use of organizational culture leads to the emergence of knowledge creation in organizations. It is suggested that in order to improve organizational culture, efforts should be made to train employees in the field of up-to-date organizational culture, and given that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on organizational structure, it is suggested that municipal employees in Mazandaran province should use organizational culture to provide a basis for the tendency of the physical structure to virtual management and work independence from place and time.

In examining the test of the second hypothesis of the study on the effect of participation on the accounting information system, it was determined that the results of examining this hypothesis are consistent with the results of previous research by researchers such as Malek Hosseini et al. (2021), Nakhaei (2020) and Ha (2020). According to the findings of this study, it can be stated that given the importance of organizational culture in an organization and having a competitive advantage, according to experts, organizational culture is also considered an undeniable thing, so that there are different views that some organizations pursue the discussion of organizational culture within the organization, while others look at the importance of this discussion in an extra-organizational manner. The emergence of the necessity of inter-organizational interactions in this field and the subsequent creation of organizations with different characteristics with the aim of facilitating inter-organizational interactions are the results of a trans-organizational view of the issue of organizational culture to recognize participation in the accounting information system, the growth and evolution of new ideas. The more senior managers of the organization pay attention to organizational culture as an inseparable category of their organization, the faster and greater the success of its implementation will be. Organizational culture is like a surgical blade if it is in the throat of the organization's manager. In this way, the belief and confidence of managers in the future is the most effective factor in the success of implementing organizational culture. In examining the test of the third hypothesis of the study, which is the lack of effect of adaptability on the accounting information system, it was determined that the results of examining this hypothesis are consistent with the results of previous research by researchers Abdipour et al. (2020); Meng & Berger (2019). In interpreting the results of this hypothesis, it can be stated that despite the importance of the category of organizational culture and the effective role that organizational culture can play in today's organizations in achieving the goals of organizational culture, just as organizational culture has been able to play an unavoidable role in the global economy due to its profound impact on most business fields from the very beginning. The lack of adaptability effect on the accounting information system by meeting the information needs of each organization can accompany them in approaching their goals. Creating a context for facilities and supporting innovation in

fundamental and applied research that is related to organizational culture with an emphasis on the organization's priorities and needs in order to make greater use of existing facilities.

In examining the test of the fourth hypothesis of the study on the effect of stability on the accounting information system, it was determined that the results of examining this hypothesis are consistent with the results of previous research by researchers Azizi et al. (2020), Meng & Berger (2019). Therefore, it can be stated that an organization is stable and remains, can exert influence, and is established in the field of the organization that improves organizational culture with important strategies. In general, by creating a specific structure, the level of organizational culture can be improved and the company's conditions can be improved, especially during the sanctions period. In order to implement the resistance economy, the use of organizational culture and the application of knowledge is one of the most important effective components that organizations should put at the forefront of their work. In this regard, the role of organizational culture is mentioned as one of the most important factors, stability in the accounting information system.

In examining the test of the fifth hypothesis of the research based on the mission on operational performance, it was determined that the results of examining this hypothesis are consistent with the results of previous research by researchers such as Shao (2019). It can be stated that turning to the mission of becoming an operational performance organization in a world full of turbulence and anomalies in all fields is essential for an organization to be able to adapt itself quickly to these problems and continue to survive actively and efficiently. In this case, society and an organization will be able to move on the path of development with great intensity and acceleration that bases its principle on this important matter. Using the great importance that organizational culture and initiative have as two important variables against turbulence and conditions, for this purpose, the risk-taking of informed managers to meet the diverse and diverse needs of customers must be increased in order to make the most of the current conditions.

In examining the test of the sixth hypothesis of the research on participation in operational performance, it was determined that the results of examining this hypothesis are consistent with the results of previous research by researchers such as Abdipour et al. (2020) and Hadid & Al-Sayed (2021). This result shows that the tendency to participate will be able to work more actively and effectively with a view to operational performance. This research is also important because the acceptance of participation on operational performance is considered an important part of the culture of an organization and has provided abundant empirical evidence on the relationship between this variable. Therefore, searching and understanding this relationship is necessary for the purpose of implementing and applying them to organizational activity and facilitating participation in operational performance.

In examining the test of the seventh hypothesis of the study based on adaptability on operational performance, it was determined that the results of examining this hypothesis are consistent with the results of previous research by researchers Hajiha & Kharatzade (2014) and Ha (2020). Since organizations can improve their activities and interact more effectively with customers through adaptability, and the factor that directly (by

responding to customers' expressed needs) and indirectly (through factors such as aggressive competition, independence, and identifying hidden needs) affects the use of knowledge is organizational management, so managers can use the knowledge and skills of individuals for new applications creatively, and also learn from mistakes in the organization, and adaptability used to solve problems is related to them.

In examining the test of the eighth hypothesis of the study, which states that stability does not affect operational performance, it was determined that the results of this hypothesis are consistent with the results of previous research by researchers Hajjabbari et al. (2013) and Tenji & Foley (2019). Stability means the existence of a common set of rules for operational performance that affects the promotion of work relationships between employees in a real and effective way at work. Organizations achieve better operational performance when these organizations are stable and implemented optimally. Given the lack of impact of stability on operational performance, companies should consider a combination of participation and stability in their work processes to promote work processes more effectively. Reliable and fast connection to the World Wide Web is to facilitate the communication of clients, managers and employees with the organization. The knowledge creation infrastructure includes hardware and development environment, databases, shared databases, shared applications and human resource skills and expertise.

In examining the test of the ninth hypothesis of the research on accounting information system on operational performance, it was determined that the results of examining this hypothesis are consistent with the results of previous research by researchers Lin et al. (2024); Siqani & Vokshi (2023); Zahedi & Nikandish (2013) and Hadid & Al-Sayed (2021). Accounting information system is evaluated as an optimal tool to improve the operational performance of an organization. In the case of an organization with a suitable accounting information system, all its activities are effective. And also, accounting information system and operational performance have a positive relationship with each other, so that when the organization has a proper accounting information system, the operational performance of the organization increases. Company managers are trying to strengthen accounting information systems according to organizational culture and have a better role in the company's performance by making its information transparent. Because the value of the accounting information system and the market value added provide different information than traditional criteria based on operational performance, companies should be ranked based on economic models of operational performance. By doing this, municipal employees will fulfill part of their information duty and help to make the capital market transparent.

In this study, the municipality of Mazandaran province was analyzed, which is one of the limitations of the present study. For future studies, it is suggested that the municipalities of other provinces be examined and the results be compared with this study. Other limitations of this study include the following: The conceptual model of this study assumes linear relationships between variables, but nonlinear effects (such as threshold or moderating effects) are not examined.

The study does not consider other variables, such as municipality size, budget constraints, or regional economic conditions. It also does not control for contextual factors that could affect AIS effectiveness and operational performance, such as

technological infrastructure, staff training levels, or regulatory compliance. These limitations could be interesting for future studies and could be the subject of future research.

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